

Photoelastic Analysis of the Behaviour of Curved Fibers in Composite

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ABSTRACT

The states of stresses in the vicinity of closed and open rings as fiber inclusions has been investigated on plane models with a special interest in shear stresses at the phase interface. These inclusions have been simulating curved fiber filler for composites with brittle matrices. The trajectories of principal shear stresses are presented for cases with orthogonal rows of inclusions, arranged also in systems with inserted full inclusions. The states of stresses are characterized by isochromatic patterns and by diagrams of principal shear stresses along some trajectories. The results prove that the curved shape of fibers meets the requirements on reinforcing fiber filler and economizes the anchoring lengths.

PROBLEM AND ITS MODELLING

The role of fibers in a composite /particulate/ system is to sustain tension or shearing stresses exceeding the respective limiting deformation of the matrix. In both cases of the straining of the composite a straight fiber resists them by its tension stress acting on its cross section. The active length of the fiber is admittedly the fiber length after subtracting the anchoring /embedding/ lengths on both ends. The shortening of these lengths means an economy in the fiber filler. The idea can occur to shorten or exclude these anchoring lengths with the form of the fiber, as is the case with the /closed or open/ ring form or a spiral element. Apart from this the ring form is an idealized limiting shape of a disordered infinite fiber as a filler in the form of a matting or a felt. Besides, the ring shape enables resisting the arising limiting strain in any direction, as is the case with particulate systems, and contributing to isotropic mechanical behavior of the system. In accordance with the identification of the defects in real composites, i.e. in the case of the microcracks /in systems with brittle matrices, where the fiber filler complements the filling part of the system/ and fracture cracks or fatigue cracks /in systems with viscoelastic matrices/, the fiber of an arbitrarily oriented cross section /a ring/ is a satisfactory barrier for braking or even a stoppage of a propagating crack.

For the nature of the problem the state of stress due to external loading is of decisive importance. This is the reason why the influence of shrinkage and other isotropic effects has not been included into the research. They can be super-

posed according to the notions known from elsewhere. Particular attention has been invariably paid to shear loading as a prevailing process of damaging the interface in the composites.

The assumed behavior of the /curved/ fiber can be realized even if such a fiber acted as an inclusion. The reduction of such an effect is achieved by the selection of a cross section and the diameter of the ring so that its spring constant will not differ from the respective elasticity modulus of the matrix.

MODELS AND LOADINGS

Photoelasticity has been resorted to as a method of investigation and the aim was to gain qualitative information about the nature of the state of shear stress in the vicinity of the ring inclusion and to examine its function with respect to the assumptions. It has proved to be satisfactory to establish a plane composite system with inclusions in the cylindrical form with the axes perpendicular to the central plane of the model and with inclusions segregated, since their mutual interaction is of minor importance for the solution of the problem. The system was occasionally supplemented by full /rigid/ inclusions that represented the particulate filler and elucidated the intensity of the reinforcing tendencies in the system /1/. An orthogonal arrangement of the system was considered.

Models of $200 \times 430 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$ size have been cold cast from epoxide resin ChS 110 by the previously worked out procedure /2/ without shrinkage. The ring inclusions of 20/1 mm diameter were from aluminium alloy as well as the full cylindrical inclusions of 10 mm diameter. The models and the arrangements of the inclusions are visualized in Fig.1. They differ only by the number and positions of inclusions. Type A has only ring inclusions in distances kept also in the other types. Type B of identical arrangement has cut ring inclusions; the cut is always located in the plane perpendicular to the direction of loading. The rings of type C are cut in the plane of loading and full inclusions in semidistances in rows. In comparison with type C, type D has closed rings and full inclusions inserted also concentrically.

The uniaxial compressive /or tensile/ loading was effected with the help of resolution of forces in the loading frame and the model was softly secured against lateral deflection. The magnitude of uniform stress was measured in the non-perturbed part of the model and used as nominal stress. Models C and D were analogously loaded also in the orthogonal direction. After the investigation in uniaxial compressive loading the models were provided with the cuts /see Fig.1/ and loaded in the central inclusion column with constant /except the external rows/ shear loading.

The Young moduli of the matrix and inclusions were 3200 MPa and 72000 MPa, respectively, the Poisson's ratios equaled 0.35 and 0.25 respectively. Full inclusions act here as perfectly rigid. However, the function of the ring inclusions is not uniquely given by their proper mechanical characteristics. The spring constant of the cut ring $e = 25 \text{ N/mm}$, which corresponds to modulus 5 MPa in simple conversion, i.e. 640 times softer than the matrix. The closed ring inclusion has / in the applied range of loading/ $e = 218.7 \text{ N/mm}$, corresponding to $E \pm 44 \text{ MPa}$, thus approximately 73 times softer. In both the cases the Poisson's ratio rises simultaneously to 1.0. The softening effect can thus not be exploited and the inclusions can utmost behave as imperfectly rigid.

The maximum loading 4.7 MPa was applied in the experiments. Only exceptionally and for illustrative documentation was it raised upto 7.5 MPa. The limite of proportionality in compression of the matrix was thus not even exceeded in stress concentrations and the presented results correspond to the linear elastic state.

After casting the models manifested a faint orientation birefringence in the interface, which did not exceed roughly 8 percent of the final birefringence under loading. In the evaluation it was therefore subtracted scalarly only. The reproducibility of the measurements on the same models proved to be reliable for the whole period of the research.

RESULTS OF MEASUREMENTS

The character of the state of stress under uniform tensile loading was identical to the compressive one and that is why this type of loading was mostly applied.

On the basis of the isoclinic curves recorded under uniaxial compressive loading σ isostatic curves /Fig. 2/ and the trajectories of the principal shear stresses /Fig. 3/ were constructed for all cases. The loading of model C and D, respectively, in the orthogonal direction yielded qualitatively equal results, as well as the loading by constant shear, and they have thus not been presented.

The information of the quantitative character of the states of stresses is furnished by the isochromatics in Figs. 4 and 5. /The values of birefringence are considered in the orders and fractions of interference fringes./ As a measure case B is made use of, for which $\sigma_0 = 3.9$ MPa, corresponding to $\sigma_0 = 2.9 \delta$.

The principal shear stresses were evaluated along the trajectories marked in Fig. 3. They were selected so that their localisation in the cases evaluated was approximately the same and would characterize the most important vicinity of the inclusions. The curves of these stresses are drawn in the diagrams in Fig. 6.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The patterns of the isoclinics in cases A, C, D, are analogous in their character, the intermediate full inclusions represent only their basic development from case A in a smaller space. Only the isoclinics of case B are of a different pattern. Here they indicate, nevertheless, only a very slight perturbation of the basic pattern, since isoclinics are particularly sensitive to a change in shape of the investigated object. Basically the character of the state of stress in all cases is the same, which is visualized by the isostatics in Fig. 2. The effect of cutting of the ring is only local. Apart from isostatics, the isochromatics too / see Fig. 5/ show that loading in the direction of the rows of inclusions does not give rise to qualitatively different state of stress under loads perpendicular to these rows.

The isostatics further show that the cut ring inclusions in case C have the same effect as the full inclusions in cases A and D. In case B an analogous situation arises for loads in the direction of the section with interrupted edge, only under loads perpendicular to this section a certain tendency arises for such inclusions to behave in a softer way. The ring inclusions accordingly act invariably as rigid /if they are compatibly filled with matrix/ and thus as concentrators of stresses. It follows that the force flows arising in such a structure both in the direction of loading or as an effect of lateral deformations will pass through the bridges between the adjoining inclusions /of any kind/ and will strain their matrices with considerable normal stresses oriented in the direction of the rows of inclusions. This is also proved by Fig. 5, where it is easily possible to identify inside the rings the tendency of the matrix to sustain isotropic state of stress. The action of the ring inclusions is thus also reinforcing.

An unfavourable effect is called forth by the free ends of the cut ring inclusions : a considerable concentration of stresses arises. This concentration is however local, it can be affected by the shape of the ends and does not provide any condition for the initiation of a running crack.

The trajectories of the principal shear stresses also document the behavior of the ring inclusions as concentrators of stress. More over they however show that - looked upon as fibers - they are capable of transmitting shear stress in any place of their circumference. All the sections of their perimeters, that these trajectories join tangentially or under a small angle, act in the same way. In places where they include an angle of approximately 45° with the tangent to the circumference of the section, and where the normal stress acting perpendicularly and tangentially to the circumference is maximum, they cross the ring wall conti-

nuously. The effect of the discontinuity of the tangential normal stress is in these cases considerably reduced.

Loading with proper shear stress in the plane of the centers of the rows of inclusions represented by isochromatics E_C , E_D in Fig. 5, proved the inclusions to be acting as rigid and shear loading to be transformed into normal force flow, so that the photoelastic patterns are congruent with those appertaining to normal loading of types C and D.

The analysis made is also confirmed by the examples of quantitative evaluation in Fig. 6. They show that the ring wall takes over the shear stress of the matrix by its normal stressing /comp. curves Nr 1 of the cases investigated/ and that these cases are in qualitative correspondance. They further show by the character of curves number 3 the influence of normal force flow in the comparatively narrow regions of the bridges between the adjoining inclusions and the tendency to take over shear stresses by the ring wall outside these regions. Finally, by the mutual position of the curves of types of types B,C,D, they show the measure of the reinforcing effect of the inclusions, which is proportional to the density of the system of inclusions. Diffusion of loading to larger regions will reduce the relative intensity of stress /loading of type B with the least filler density is half of that of types C and D/. The straining of the matrix enclosed in the inclusion is, however, relatively rising.

The results obtained enable theoretical confirmation of the assumption of the application of the ring or similarly curved fibers as reinforcement against microcracks and also as barriers to propagating cracks, particularly in composites with brittle matrices. By effective shortening of the anchoring lengths of the fibers they further enable increasing their exploitation, and contributing to the simplification of the production technology of mixtures.

REFERENCES

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Fig. 1. Size of models and arrangement of inclusions [mm]. Uniform compressive /left/ and constant shear loading /right/.

Fig. 6. Curves of maximum shear stresses along trajectories marked in Fig.2. Loading ratio in individual cases B:C:D = 1:1.9:1.9.

Fig. 2. Isostatics in details of models A, B, C, D, investigated. Principal stresses σ_1 - full lines, σ_2 - dashed lines.

Fig. 3. Trajectories of the principal shear stresses τ_{\max} in details of models A,B,C,D, investigated. Principal directions distinguished by full and dashed lines.

Fig. 4. Isochromatics in the vicinity of rings without full inclusions. Loading by uniform perpendicular stress σ : $A/\sigma = 3.4 \mathcal{J}/$, $A_{\max}/\sigma = 21.2 \mathcal{J}/$, $B/\sigma_0 = 2.9 \mathcal{J}/$.

Fig. 5. Isochromatics of systems with full inclusions. C' , D' - perpendicular loading $\sigma/\sigma_0 = 5.6 \mathcal{J}/$, C'' - horizontal loading $\sigma/\sigma_0 = 2.8 \mathcal{J}/$. E_C , E_D - loading by proper shear in the axes of the column of inclusions $\tau/\tau_0 = 2.4 \mathcal{J}/$.